

Valorizing Hedge Trimmings into Compost in a Continental Climate

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Shredder processing hedge trimmings into wood chips for composting

The maintenance of a mature hedge generates significant amounts of green waste. These pruning residues can be shredded to produce ramial chipped wood (RCW). It can then be spread or composted to make the nitrogen it contains available to crops. At the *Ferme des Rufaux*, windbreak hedges were planted in 2012 to surround the 2-hectare plot and separate it from the neighboring cereal crops. These hedges consist of 80% willow (*Salix viminalis*), planted one meter apart, for its rapid growth and melliferous properties, and 20% tall-growing trees (willows, oaks, catalpas, wild cherries, elderberries, dogwoods, spindle trees, etc.). Since 2013, maintenance pruning has been carried out every 2 to 3 years by a professional on the old hedges of the farm to avoid having to cut large-diameter branches. In the winter of 2022, a major pruning of the new hedge allowed for the collection of a significant amount of wood. A telescopic loader and a disc mower were borrowed from neighboring farmers, and a shredder from the CUMA was used to turn the branches into RCW (Ramial Chipped Wood). Since he usually buys compost from outside, he decided to compost this RCW. Unfortunately, stored in a large heap, the RCW lost a significant portion of its nutrients due to the development of cyanobacteria, which led to excessive mineralization. It was therefore used as mulch in the walking spaces between vegetable beds. By 2024, the willow regrowth has already reached 7 to 8 meters in height. The hedge, which stretches over 300 linear meters, was pruned with a bilateral cut to reduce its width to 3 meters, while cutting it back to a height of 4 meters, at a total cost of 400€ (€95 per hour). The pruning residues were shredded and composted this time in windrows of 20 to 30 meters long and 1.5 meters high, following the advice of a specialist, to produce good quality compost.

Camille Archambaud

Ver de Terre Production

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